

Solid State Interaction Between Zinc Phosphate and Urea Nitrate

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Manuscript received 15 February 1976, accepted 8 December 1976

Zinc phosphate reacts with urea nitrate when the powders of the two solids are ground together for 1-2 hours. The resulting product becomes completely water soluble when the mole ratio of tribasic zinc phosphate to urea nitrate is 1:4 and may be utilized as a suitable fertilizer for nitrogen, phosphorus and zinc deficient soils. The interaction occurs in two steps: (i) formation of $ZnHPO_4$ in the solid phase and (ii) conversion of $ZnHPO_4$ to $Zn(H_2PO_4)_2$ in the solid-liquid phase.

AMONG different micronutrients, zinc deficiencies are more wide spread in the Indo-Gangetic plains of Punjab, Haryana and Uttar Pradesh*. It has been reported by a large number of workers^{1,2,4,7} that heavier doses of phosphatic fertilizers induce deficiency and unavailability of zinc to plants. In the present investigation an attempt has therefore been made to explore the conditions for the manufacture of a mixed fertilizer suitable to supply zinc in presence of phosphorus in the zinc deficient soils, on the lines recently reported by Pant and Pathak³. The work consists of grinding varying amounts of urea nitrate with a fixed amount of tribasic zinc phosphate. The ratio of urea nitrate to zinc phosphate which makes the resulting product completely water soluble has been investigated.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were BDH AnalaR grade.

A series of mixtures were prepared by mixing 1g mole of zinc phosphate, $Zn_3(PO_4)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ with varying amounts of urea nitrate and each mixture was ground in an agate mortar for 1-2 hours under dry conditions.

Water soluble and citrate soluble phosphates in the ground mixtures were determined by methods reported in an earlier communication⁶. Phosphorus was estimated volumetrically after precipitating with molybdate solution and zinc was estimated gravimetrically as zinc pyrophosphate⁸.

The amount of zinc nitrate formed in the ground mixture was estimated by leaching with absolute alcohol in a soxhlet extractor. Since zinc phosphate is insoluble in ethanol the amount of zinc present in the solvent is originating from the zinc nitrate formed.

Discussion

The experimental results (Table 1) indicate that with increasing urea nitrate content, the percentage of water soluble phosphate gradually increases, finally resulting in cent per cent water soluble mixtures.

Unprotonated zinc phosphate may react with urea nitrate either when the two reactants are mixed or when the mixture is placed in water. In the former case, zinc nitrate is one of the products and is

TABLE 1. WATER AND CITRATE SOLUBLE P_2O_5 IN ZINC PHOSPHATE-UREA NITRATE MIXTURE.

Zinc phosphate to urea nitrate mole ratio	Total P_2O_5 %	Water soluble P_2O_5 %	Citrate soluble P_2O_5 %	Fraction of water soluble P_2O_5 %	Fraction of citrate soluble P_2O_5 %
1 : 0	30.99	—	—	—	—
1 : 1.00	24.43	8.28	7.92	33.48	32.41
1 : 1.50	22.06	10.78	4.47	48.86	20.26
1 : 2.00	20.01	11.05	3.73	55.22	18.64
1 : 2.50	18.47	12.60	3.12	68.21	16.89
1 : 3.00	17.16	14.64	2.72	85.31	15.85
1 : 3.25	16.60	15.32	1.03	92.89	6.20
1 : 3.50	15.98	15.19	0.41	95.07	2.58
1 : 3.75	15.44	15.26	—	98.77	—
1 : 4.00	14.94	14.93	—	99.98	—

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soluble in solvents other than water. Hence absolute alcohol is used as the extracting medium. Zinc could be detected in solution, while no phosphate was found in the alcohol. Urea as well as urea nitrate is soluble in the alcohol and only zinc phosphate is left behind as the residue. The zinc nitrate formed in the ground mixture of tri zinc phosphate and urea nitrate is estimated and results are given in Table 2. The zinc nitrate content increases with increasing amount of urea nitrate and

It is well known that when an excess amount of tribasic phosphate reacts with less amount of an aqueous acid, a mixture of dibasic phosphate and monobasic phosphosphate is obtained. But the protonation of zinc phosphate by urea nitrate follows a path other than that expected in an aqueous medium. This is supported by the fact that $Zn(H_2PO_4)_2$ is not produced in step (i). Had it been one of the products the side reaction :

TABLE 2. ZINC NITRATE CONTENT IN ETHANOL EXTRACT [ZINC PHOSPHATE (9.1622 g)+UREA NITRATE]

Wt. of urea nitrate (g)	Zinc phosphate to urea nitrate mole ratio	No. of g atoms of zinc soluble in alcohol per mole of zinc phosphate
1.23	1 : 0.50	0.1560
2.46	1 : 1.00	0.4010
3.69	1 : 1.50	0.8160
4.92	1 : 2.00	1.2800
5.53	1 : 2.25	1.2780
6.15	1 : 2.50	1.2420
7.38	1 : 3.00	1.2620

would occur and urea phosphate, $CO(NH_2)_2 \cdot H_3PO_4$ soluble in absolute alcohol would have been the resulting product. Since no alcohol soluble phosphate is detected in the ground mixture of urea nitrate and zinc phosphate the possibility of formation of $Zn(H_2PO_4)_2$ in the (i) step is completely ruled out. Hence it is concluded that $ZnHPO_4$ formed in the (i) step dissolves in excess urea nitrate solution to form $Zn(H_2PO_4)_2$ in the (ii) step, rendering the whole mixture water soluble.

reaches a limiting value when the mole ratio of zinc phosphate to urea nitrate is 1 : 2. Further increase in the urea nitrate content does not give rise to increased amount of zinc nitrate in the extract. The limiting value of zinc nitrate found corresponds to one mole for every mole of tri zinc phosphate mixed with two moles of urea nitrate.

The experimental results clearly indicate that a ground mixture of tribasic zinc phosphate and urea nitrate in the mole ratio of 1 : 4 is a good source of nitrogen, phosphorus and zinc to plants and therefore may be utilized as a suitable fertilizer for the nutrient deficient soils of different parts of India.

It is clear from the above observation that the interaction between urea nitrate and unprotonated zinc phosphate occurs in the following two steps :

The first step is a solid phase reaction whereas the second step is a solid-liquid phase reaction in which the nitric acid formed by the dissociation of urea nitrate reacts with dibasic zinc phosphate produced in the first step. This is further supported by the fact that at the later stage of grinding the powders form a paste.

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